

The Relative and the Absolute – The Path from the Profane to the Sacred in Lodge

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ABSTRACT

How to move from the relative to the sacred? This is the fundamental question for the mason in a lodge.

What are the steps planned in the ritual?

Who are the main actors?

With which tools ?

What about the state of mind of Brothers ?

The analysis of the modern Belgian ritual of the Regular Grand Lodge of Belgium allowed me to answer these questions.

The path from the relative to the sacred implies a lot of knowledge, as well as the symbolic presence of the Ein-Sof.

1. The Path from Profane World to The Sacred

The Apprentice brothers have often asked at what moment, "the lodge passes from the profane to the sacred." My first answer was the following: a lodge is a sacred space "in the making" or exactly, "in potential" for the path to the sacred.

But concretely, it is thanks to the well-known and well-used ritual, with the helpful participation of the Brothers wanting to realize this moment, that the path from the profane to the sacred can be realized.

Main various actors will intervene: the Worshipful Master, the two wardens, as well as the Master of Ceremonies. But to this are, of course, added the Brother of the Column of Harmony (music) and all the Brothers participating in this path to the sacred.

This path is very rich in symbolism and involves the symbolic knowledge of tools and texts. To open the lodge, there is therefore the use of specific tools such as the Volume of the sacred law, the square and the compass, actors and the use of a well-executed ritual. To this, we can add the positive state of mind of the brothers.

At the opening of the lodge works, the Worshipful Master adapts the square of the lodge. Having got rid of his metals, he carves this square in the circle of time, giving birth to the sacred Temple, between the Nadir and the Zenith.

Then appear the four dimensions, in a universe known only to the children of the Light. The four dimensions thus create the spatial-temporal equation of the lodge.

The brothers can finally work from Noon to Midnight, then receive their salaries at the respective columns "J" and "B".

This is how we pass from the relative to the absolute.

The opening of the Lodge is therefore a celebration that is based on a special rite that has its own ritual. The ritual is therefore repetitive, like a reminder of each outfit, this celebration allowing to pass from the profane world to a sacred space where time and space no longer count.

It is in this esoteric crucible that "VITRIOL" is located and the theological virtues Faith - Hope - Charity must emerge, accompanied by the cardinal values. The metals remain outside the Temple where the outfits are made "to the glory of the great architect of the universe".

Note that for Freemasonry of the Judeo-Christian essence, the manifestation of the divine, which is Ein Sof, is done through knowledge. Freemasonry seeks light and truth, without, however, being able to possess them.

It is during the work of the lodge, at midday, in a sacred space, that the masons cut their stones to improve themselves and try to obtain more light.

This research, which is in the domain of the search for spirituality, can only be done by getting rid of metals to focus all one's energy on spiritual and not material research.

Masonic artwork:

Le chœur des chauves, Gouache, 27x36, 1999, Ferenc Sebök

2. Analysis of The Ritual

In the ritual of the ancient and accepted Scottish rite, we can cite some excerpts that lead to this mutation of the profane world towards the sacred.

The Master of Ceremonies Said This:

(Belgian Modern ritual of the Regular grand lodge of Belgium)

"My Brothers, the Worshipful Master calls us to work!"

The Worshipful Master Said the Following to The Master of Ceremonies:

"...Please lead us there."

"...Brother Master of the Column of Harmony help us to leave the Profane world with appropriate accents." (music)

"...What is the first duty of a Warden in a lodge?" »

And The Senior Warden Answers:

"...It is to make sure that the Lodge is covered (tyled) externally..."

...It is to make sure that all those who compose the assembly are masons..."

The Worshipful Master Asks a Question to The Junior Warden Who Answers Him This:

"...To better observe the Sun at its Meridian, to send the Workers from work to recreation and call them from recreation to work, so that the Master draws honour and contentment therefrom..."

And The Senior Warden Answers This:

"...As the Sun sets in the West to close the day, so the Brother Senior Warden stands there to help the Worshipful Master to close the Lodge, pay the Workers and send them away happy and satisfied..."

The Worshipful Master Asks:

"...where is the Worshipful Master standing?..."

The Senior Warden Answers This:

"As the Sun sets in the West to close the day, so the Brother Senior Warden stands there to help the Worshipful Master to close the Lodge, to pay the Workers and to send them away happy and satisfied..."

The Worshipful Master Asks:

“...where is the Worshipful Master standing?...”

The Senior Warden Answers This:

“As the Sun sets in the West to close the day, so the Brother Senior Warden stands there to help the Worshipful Master to close the Lodge, to pay the Workers and to send them away happy and satisfied...”

The Worshipful Master Asks:

“...where is the Worshipful Master standing?...”

The Senior Warden Answers This:

“... .. rises in the East to open the day, likewise, the Worshipful Master stands there to open the Lodge, direct it in its Works and illuminate it with his Lights”.

After this, the candles will be lit at the three columns: Wisdom - Strength - Beauty. The Lodge Table is uncovered.

Then the Worshipful Master will open the Volume of the Sacred Law to the page of the Prologue of Saint John and place the square on the compass, at the degree of apprentices.

It is only at this moment that the brothers have left the Profane world to enter the sacred, the path from the relative to the absolute.

But the Worshipful Master must still celebrate this special moment.

The Worshipful Master Celebrates This Moment by Attesting This:

“To the Glory of the Great Architect of the Universe, in the name of universal Freemasonry, under the auspices of the Grand Lodge..., by virtue of the powers conferred upon me, I declare open to the degree of Apprentice, this Respectable Lodge of Saint John, constituted in the East of..., under the number... and the distinctive sign... (Name of the lodge)”

(By this act, it is formally the opening of the Lodge)

And The Worshipful Master Continues:

“...My Brothers, we are no longer in the Profane world. We have left our metals at the door of the Lodge. Let us raise our hearts in brotherhood and let our eyes turn towards the Light... »
(Symbolically, the East)

At the end of the masonic meeting, the closing of the lodge's work, the ritual provides for a closing celebration to pass from the sacred to the profane world. For this event, the Worshipful Master must close the Lodge's Work, with three knocks struck in the East, then with three knocks in the South (Senior warden) and three knocks in the West (Junior warden).

However, on certain occasions, notably during the winter and summer solstice meetings, or during other special events, the sacred is also present outside the Temple of the Lodge. The masonic meeting can therefore be continued by "ritual Agapes", also called "table ritual" or "Harmony" in the Scottish rite.

Fraternal Agapes are therefore not always table rituals. The table ritual, where the Agapes take place, is in a way an extension of the work of a Masonic meeting, with the masonic decorations (Aprons, gloves, etc.) carried by the brothers.

Otherwise, the Worshipful Master closes the works and then the masons remove their masonic decorations to go to the "Wet Room" (so called in French rite) to participate in the Agapes, without ritual. The ritual tells us precisely when the Lodge passes from the profane to the sacred. There is a whole process coded in the ritual whose apotheosis occurs when the Worshipful Master says:

"My brothers, the works are open."

However, he can say this only if everything has been set up according to the ritual and he has made sure that the lodge is tyled (protected from the profane). It is also necessary that the three columns (Wisdom - Strength - Beauty) are lit, that the tracing board in the first degree is uncovered and that on the altar, the three lights of Freemasonry are placed adequately: Volume of the sacred law and square on the compass.

What can we read in the Scottish ritual about the opening Lodge, concerning the path to the sacred dimension?

Worshipful Master:

« The first great care of Masons when convened? »

Inner Guard:

« To see that the Lodge is duly tyled »

...

Worshipful Master:

« How are we tyled? »

Inner Guard

« By an Entered Apprentice without, armed with the proper implement of his office »

...

So due to the ritual, the gate of the Temple is shut for profanes. And the Inner Guard answer to the Worshipful Master:

« To observe the approach of cowans and eavesdroppers, see that none pass or re-pass except such as are duly qualified and have permission from the Worshipful Master »

...

Senior Warden

« All present are Entered Apprentices, Worshipful Master »

The password will be requested to ensure once again the quality of the masons.
And the ritual continues...

One can easily see great differences between the modern Belgian rite or the modern French rite and the Scottish rite with regard to the opening of the Lodge; however, this is not the subject of this article.

It can be noted, however, that the path from the profane to the sacred shows differences, but the Masonic goal is the same.

Masonic triptych:

« Les Vrais Amis », Acrylic and oil, 320x200, 2011, Ferenc Sebök.

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